

**IMPLEMENTING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN NIGERIA: ROLES OF THE SPECIAL EDUCATOR
(CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD)**

Zakariyah, Ibrahim (Ph.D)

Department of Special Education,
Niger State College of Education, Minna
+2348032464622
babafili0185@gmail.com

and

Lazarus, Kelechi U. (Ph.D)

Department of Special Education,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria
+2348032322859

Abstract

This paper focused on implementing inclusive education in Nigeria: roles of special educators, challenges and ways forward. The paper made an in depth analysis of inclusive education, categories of special educators and their roles, which are inclusive of practical instructions, record keeping, curriculum, assessment and leadership. The paper equally explored the reasons for the practice of the 1990 Jomtien World Conference's Education for All agenda, which guided the development of inclusive education. The difficulties in implementing inclusive education, inclusive education principles in Nigeria, inclusive education trends globally, inclusive education-supporting laws, recommendations, conclusions, and next steps were also reviewed.

Keywords: Special educator; Practice of inclusive education in Nigeria; Learners with special needs; Individualised instructional programmes

Introduction

Many authors have given different definitions of inclusive education. For example, some have defined it as placing all students, with and without special needs, in the same classrooms and schools, providing them with equal access to educational opportunities and facilities, regardless of their similarities and differences. According to Ahmad (2010), inclusive education involves teaching all kids and young adults—with and without impairments or learning challenges—in regular pre-primary schools, colleges, and universities with the right kind of network support. According to Okwudire and Okechukwu (2018) inclusive education refers to the growth in student engagement and the decrease in their exclusion from the communities, cultures, and curricula of nearby schools. They went on to say that inclusive education allows all students no matter their talents or limitations, learners are treated equally at school and are not marginalized, either within or outside of the classroom. To prepare students for productive lives and to contribute fully to society. Ibok (2015) defined inclusive education as offering equitable opportunities for all students, including those with significant disabilities, to receive effective educational services along with the necessary supplementary aids and support, as well as appropriate classrooms.

The idea of "mainstreaming" and "integration," which in the past indicated accommodating all learner categories in the classroom and were primarily concerned with individuals with special needs, is not the same as the trend of inclusive education (Wikipedia 2014, www.file.scirp.org). Every effort is made to uphold the learner's right to an education and to allow the child, regardless of disability, to fully participate in schoolwork and programs.

National Centre on Educational Restructuring and Inclusion (1995), defined Inclusive Education to mean:

Providing to all students, including those with significant disabilities, equitable opportunities to receive effective educational services, with the needed supplementary aids and support services, in age-appropriate classrooms, in order to prepare students for productive lives as full members of society (p 1).

The platform of the 1990 World Conference in Johannesburg, entitled "Education for All (EFA)," provided the first global testimony of inclusive education. Every child, youth, adult, and person should be able to benefit from educational opportunities that should meet their basic learning needs, according to the conference report, which was mandatory for all signatory countries, including Nigeria (World Conference for Education for All 1990). The 1994 Educational Report followed, which provided the concept of inclusive education with more momentum. Likewise, the problem of students being completely shut out of or marginalized inside the educational system was taken seriously six years later, in April 2000, at the Dakar World Education Forum.

The key challenge is to ensure that a broad vision of Education For All as an inclusive concept is reflected in national government and funding agency policies (UNESCO, 2000).

In order to ensure that "No One Left Behind," inclusive education was not developed in a vacuum or as a short-term solution. Rather, it is an approach to a comprehensive system review and reform that includes reviewing the entire educational system to increase participation and quality while also involving all social segments such as the family, school, and community systems. Additional research revealed that many strategies and tactics used to raise involvement and learning for individuals with special education needs also work effectively to raise learning for other kids (UNESCO, undated).

Access, quality, and community involvement are the three main pillars of inclusive education (i.e. parents, schools, communities, and civil society). The first obstacle in the enormous battle for inclusive education is access—the right to go to a regular school for kids with exceptional needs. Quality means that both individuals and children with disabilities can learn in an acceptable manner assessment which can encompass behavioural and social as well as academic benchmarks. Community participation is the third aspect of inclusive education, it's so important because providing support from parents, schools, communities and civil society is paramount to survival and strive for them to take their place equally in the society (UNESCO, 2008).

The function of special educators in putting inclusive education into practice

A special educator works with children of all ages who have cognitive, emotional, or physical problems. They have received specialized training on how to work effectively with children and people with special needs. The special educator is a professional who may work in classroom, resource centers or any place of need to help people with special needs or they may work in inclusive classrooms where they assist regular classroom teacher where they provide students with special needs with specialised attention and unique approaches they need to develop their full potential. The special educator often provides Individualized Educational Programmes (IEPs) to set goals and track each student's progress. Special educator collaborates and coordinates with other professionals, guidance counselors to prepare lessons and write reports. They also from time to time communicate directly with the parents and guardian of students with special needs about their reports (www.careerexplorer.com). Special educators are group into the following categories:

- i. i. Special educators for behavioral or emotional disorders: A special educator is a trained professional with specialized knowledge in behavioral and emotional disorders. They help students with learning difficulties who suffer from anxiety disorders, attention deficit disorders, depression, hyperactivity disorders, and other behavioral disorders.
- ii. **Special educator for autism spectrum disorder:** Student suffering from autism is usually unable to correlate in many circumstances; they usually have delay in communicating and are always backward in relationship. A special educator with specialization in autism spectrum disorder provides learning support to those children.
- iii. **Special educator in the college:** a professionally trained special educator provides teaching and learning to students with special needs in the college.

A special educator generally helps students with special needs learn the same information and skills the way normal students learn in the class, only that their work may be challenging and sometimes it can also be satisfying to help these children reach their potentials and see them prosper www.in.indeed.com.

Fisher, Frey & Thousand (2003), summarized the role of special educator in an inclusive setting to be:

Instructional role: The duty of instructing some students in adapting facilities and instruction, provides small group instruction, teaching all the class, monitored and evaluate students' academic work, coordinating support (academics, medical, behavioural needs) for individual students.

Assessment role: Grading students' performance in tests and examinations, developing appropriate exhibition as at when due and demonstration of student work as well as administering educational test.

Communication role: planning and attending meetings, attending problem solving meetings, communicating with parents, attending family meetings, as well as providing information about inclusive education.

Leadership role: A leader is to train, supervise and guide the professionals, he or she is also to coordinate peer tutoring, facilitate the use of professional gadgets, and encourage the use of natural materials as well as support friendship.

Record keeping: In record keeping, it requires records of student's performance and maintaining proper records of curriculum accommodations and modifications, as well as the record of Individual Educational Programs (IEPs). www.wholeschooling.net.

Global trends in inclusive education

The global agitation for inclusive education came into being in the world conference on EFA agenda in Spain as a result of persistent attention on the needs to take off obstacles and hindrances on participation and training out of school children globally of which children with special needs make up majority which is estimated up to 90 percent as at then. By right every child has equal access to education, and majority of out of school children have moderate impairment, most of these impairments are not visible and are difficult to locate and define (World Bank, 2003). The 1948 and 1989 Universal Declaration of Human Rights and United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989, are the most widely ratified treaty in history, signed a comprehensive framework of legal binding instrument guarantee the right of all children to education (UNICEF, 2005). Another powerful document that supports the right to education of people with disability is the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which states that persons with disabilities are not excluded from the general education system on the basis of disability and should receive reasonable accommodation and support required to learn. The article specifically mentioned the provision of sign language and braille for individuals who are deaf and blind respectively (www.unsaid.gov).

Why Inclusive Education?

- i. In order to include students who were previously disadvantaged and excluded from education due to imperfections that are not their "barriers to learning," inclusive education is a system of instruction that supports all students regardless of their abilities and disabilities. These obstacles can be of the

following types: physical, mental, psycho-social, neurological, emotional, beliefs, color and racial, religious, socioeconomic, and gender. Due to these obstacles, all states parties are required by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities to guarantee inclusive education at all levels in order to ensure that No One Is Left Behind (NOLB) and that everyone succeeds (UN, 2006). Wikipedia(2014) stated two varieties;

- ii. Partial inclusion is a type of education system in which students with special needs spend almost all or at least half of the day in regular classrooms, receiving specialized instruction outside of it as needed. Examples of these services include speech, physical, and hearing therapy, as well as braille writing and reading.
- iii. Full inclusion: All kids receive an education in which they are fully integrated into a single school setting. This will include those who need professional services in a typical school setting, such as behavioral and educational support, medical care, and rehabilitation.

Whatever approach is chosen for inclusive education, it is important to remember that its fundamental components are that it involves a "never-ending search to find better ways of responding to diversity," the use of diverse evidence to spark problem-solving and creativity, the identification and removal of barriers to education for all, and, most importantly, "the presence of all children in schools and participating to succeed together." Additionally, equal opportunities and considerations for "group of learners who may be at risk of marginalization exclusion or under achievement" (Ainscow, 2004) in researchgate.net) are all aspects of inclusive education.

Children with different levels of intellectual disability can learn alongside ordinary students in the same classroom setting thanks to inclusive education (Bassegy et al., 2020). Isah (2014) emphasized that inclusive education aims to provide students with disabilities with the opportunity to participate as members in all school activities and also assert their entitlement to such opportunities, in addition to placing special education students in general education classrooms. It follows that all students who participate in this way develop and maintain teamwork, which in turn helps them to give their fair share to the growth of the country.

Aniefiok, James, and Michael, (2020) further explained that, inclusive education is directed to sustain, promote and recognised the right to education for all and its provision devoid of discrimination against no one so as to address the diverse needs of all learners irrespective of their parental economic status, religious background, geographical location, ability, disability, ethnic group and language. Specifically, inclusive education in this context, is educational policy that accommodates all the learners with and without any form of impairment (disabilities) or difficulties in learning and does not put in to consideration age, sex, tribe, religion, cultural and economic background, as well as physical, mental, emotional and psychological abilities of the learners in all cadres of education, early childhood/elementary, middle or tertiary (i.e. pre-primary, primary, secondary as well as tertiary) levels. It could also be stressed that, inclusive education is designed to equalize educational opportunities in one learning environment for all the children and youths (handicapped, disabled, and gifted/talented) so that at the end they could fully play their role by contributing towards national development. With inclusive education, every pupil/student has the right to attend any school of his or her choice irrespective of school ownership (public and private). In a typical inclusive setting, the marginalized groups or the excluded are included in the teaching and learning processes. This informs that inclusive education is directed towards ensuring that, every learner in education system is entitled to equal education and learning opportunities irrespective of his socio-economic background and physical, emotional and mental strength and weakness. It aims at improving healthy cooperation among all the students irrespective of their strength and weaknesses, as well as abilities and disabilities (www.earjournals.com)

In general, inclusive education aims to normalize living and learning conditions for children with special needs in a classroom setting alongside their peers, as well as fostering community interaction. It also reduces costs for school administrators. Stated differently, resources that might otherwise be allocated to distinct special schools are committed elsewhere (Chuka, 2013). In addition to teaching each other better academic outcomes and identifying individual differences, it also increases understanding and acceptance of diverse cultures, respects adult life, fosters meaningful friendships, increases participation, acceptance, and appreciation of one another, creates awareness and opportunities for mastery of activities through constant practice, and ensures that all students' needs are met (Daramola & Kaduhur, 2013).

Principles of Inclusive Education

Inclusive Education (IE) was built on the following principles according to cedefop.europa.eu in Reddy, (2016):

Principle I: Expanding the participation gap to give every student more educational opportunities:

Expanding educational chances and supporting full participation and possibilities for all learners who are at risk of exclusion are the primary objectives of inclusive education, enabling them to reach their full potential in the classroom. In order to effectively promote high-quality inclusive education, the following aspects must be taken into account: A broader spectrum of students than just those classified as having special educational needs are the focus of inclusive education. Any student who runs the risk of being excluded from educational opportunities and failing their classes is the focus of inclusive education.

Principle II: Education and training of all teachers in inclusive education:

The success of inclusive education depends partly on all the teachers, for effective inclusive settings, all teachers need to have appropriate values, attitudes, skills and competences, knowledge and understanding. Meaning that all teachers should be prepared to work in inclusive education in their initial training and then have access to further their education, to go for in-service training in order to refresh their knowledge and develop skills to enhance their inclusive practice in inclusive settings.

Principle III: Organizational culture and attitudes that promote inclusive education:

School is one of the elements of change, a shared culture and attitude based upon positive ethos towards welcoming a diversity of learners from different backgrounds in the same classrooms and meeting diverse needs in education is crucial. Such a diverse culture: includes all the stakeholders in educational sector; learners of all categories; their families; teachers and workers in the school. Local community is guided by school inclusive educational organization leaders with a vision that includes robust thinking regarding school development, accountability and responsibility for meeting a diverse range of needs. Organizational cultures that are supportive of inclusion result in: a practice that avoids segregation in all forms and promotes a school for all, providing qualitative educational for all learners; a culture of ones, team

Principle IV: Support architectural barrier free environment to promote inclusion:

Support buildings that are architectural barrier free for people with special needs, impact upon inclusion are diverse and often involve a range of different service professionals, approaches and working methods. Established support structures can act as motivator to, or as a barrier to inclusive education. Support buildings that promote inclusive education are: composed of a range of different professional services, organizations and resource centers, and specialists that reflect local level needs. Support structures should be able to respond flexibly to a range of organizational, as well as individual professional and family level needs; challenges of inclusion co-ordinate both within and between different sectors (education, health, social services etc.), and teams of support professionals. Co-ordinate so as to support in the best way possible successful transitions.

Principle V: Flexible resourcing systems that promote inclusion

Funding policy remain one of the most powerful factor that determine the success or failure of inclusive education, so funding and structures remain the most significant agents for a successful inclusive education. Little or no access to certain facilities and provision of certain items may actually hinder the full success and quality of opportunity for learners with special educational needs. There should be mechanisms in place for funding and resourcing of education that promote inclusion rather than hinder inclusion.

Principle VI: Good policies that promote inclusion

There should be good and sustainable policies that will promote inclusive education for all. The goal for education for all should be promoted in the educational policies and the promotion of quality in inclusive education requires a clearly stated policy. Policies that support school culture, leadership, as well as mode of teachers' practice to promote quality in inclusive education: putting into consideration the account of international level policies and initiatives; so flexible enough to reflect local level needs; maximize the factors supporting inclusion as outlined above for the individual learners and their parents at the teacher and educational organization levels. There also should be effective communication with all stakeholders at all levels (iaus.archive.org).

Principle VII: Good legislation that promote inclusion

Legislations are backbone of all policies, legislations that potentially impacts upon inclusive education within a country should clearly state inclusion as a goal. Consequently legislations across all public sectors should lead to the provision of services that enhance developments and processes working towards inclusion in education. In particular, there should be: 'Integrated' legislation across sectors leading to consistency between inclusive education and other policy initiatives; one legal framework covering inclusive education in all educational sectors and levels. For a successful inclusion, Nigeria must have a comprehensive and co-ordinate legislation for inclusive education that fully addresses issues of flexibility, diversity, and equity in all educational institutions for all learners. It ensures that all policy provision and supports are consistent across all geographical areas of country/regions.

Challenges of Inclusive Education

Challenges faced by inclusive education in Nigeria since inception is funding, UNESCO (2009) concluded that the major challenges to inclusive education in Nigeria is funding. Teaching children with disabilities in general education classrooms take specialists and additional classrooms to support students' needs. Coordinating services and offering individual support to children requires additional money that many schools do not have, particularly in a tight economy. Therefore, inadequate funding can hinder ongoing professional development that helps keep specialist and classroom teachers updated on the best practices.

Implementation of Inclusive education in Nigeria and Most developing countries of the world

Attitudes and behaviour greatly contribute to implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria, negative attitude and behaviours on the part of educators and parents, in relation to the skills children with disabilities to learn. In some cases children with special learning needs are neglected and some see them as outcasts, demons or curses to the family despite all efforts on awareness campaign. Based on the submission of Cortiella as reported by Akinyi, Ezekiel, and Orodho (2015) they asserted that, lack of modern learning instructional materials, shortage of educational resources, lack of teachers, shortage of professionally trained qualified staff are major challenges. Another constrain is the policy makers who do not understand the concept of inclusive education can be a barrier to implementation of inclusive education (Ainscow & Booth, 2006).

Conclusions

Inclusive education involves active academic activities and programmes for all learners in the same learning environment irrespective of sex, tribe, religion, cultural and economic background as well physical, mental,

emotional and psychological abilities, which in the long run creates and sustains collaboration among all learners who will subsequently contribute their quotas to national development by working together. Inclusive education requires professionally trained special educators, a conducive learning environment that is well equipped with resources that will enhance effective teaching of learners with special needs and backed up with policies to support the implementation of the subject matter which is inclusion in Nigeria.

Suggestions on the way forward towards implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria

For effective inclusion in Nigeria, the paper suggests that:

1. There should be accurate and concrete data (census) of learners with special education needs for proper planning and sustainability in terms of expected enrolment of required professionals to fit in for the programme, infrastructural needs and equipments, teacher learner ratio among others.
2. Adequate funds should be provided by the federal government for recruitment of the professionally trained special education teachers and procurement of facilities and resources.
3. Training and retraining of special education teachers as well as regular classroom teachers on the best classroom practices should be put in place by the government prior to the utilization of the facilities.
4. Adequate resources which include classrooms, desks, text books, large prints, on screen reading, compact

References

- Ahmad, A. (2010). *Inclusive education for children with special needs: Problems and prospects*. A paper presented at The 11th National Council for Exceptional Children's Annual Conference. Okene
- Ainscow, M. & Booth, N. (2006). *Improving schools, developing inclusion*. London: Routledge.
- Ainscow, M. (2004). *Developing Inclusive Education Systems: What Are the Levers for Change?* Manchester: The University of Manchester.
- Akinyi, L. E., Ezekiel, O. N., & Orodho, J. A. (2015). Challenges Facing Implementation of Inclusive Education in Public Secondary Schools in Rongo Sub-County, Migori County, Kenya. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*.4 (1). Pp39-50.
- Aniefiok, O. E., James, E. O., & Michael, E. A. (2020). Administrative Strategies and Implementation of Inclusive Education for National Development: A Focus on Public Primary and Secondary Schools in Cross River State, Nigeria, Nigeria. *Journal of the Social Sciences*,48(4)
- Chukuka, E. U. (2013). Barriers to effective implementation of inclusive education in Nigeria. *National Journal of Inclusive Education*.1 (1), 186–192
- Daramola, I. S. & Kaduhur, D. B. (2013). Role of technical teachers in promoting inclusive education programme in technical colleges in Nigeria. *National Journal of Inclusive Education*.1 (1), 119–125
- Fisher, D., Frey, N. & Thousand, J. (2003). What do Special Educators Need to Know and Be Prepared to Do for Inclusive Schooling to Work? *Teacher Education and Special Education*.26(1). Pp42–50
- Ibok, R. L. (2015). Reformation of primary school curriculum: A panacea for social change for 21st century. *Journal of Education Research*,4(2),1-17.
- Okwudire, A. M., & Okechukwu, O. (2018). Inclusive education prospects for Children with autism and challenges for educational planners. *The Exceptional Child*,10(2),370-377.
- Reddy, M. R. (2016). Principles of Promoting Quality in Inclusive Education. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*.3(3) ISBN:978-1-365-03419pp2349-3429.
- UNESCO, (2005). *Guidelines for Inclusion: Ensuring Access to Education for All*. Paris, France.
- UNESCO, (2008). *The Road to 2015: Reaching the Education Goals*. Paris, France.
- UNESCO, (2009). Defining an inclusive education agenda: Reflections around the 48th session of the International Conference on Education. Geneva: UNESCOIBE.

UNESCO, (undated). *Educating Children and Young People with Disabilities*. Hagerty, S.

United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006).

United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (2000). *The Dakar Framework for Action*.

World Bank (2003). *Education for All: Including Children with Disabilities in Education Notes*, August 2003.